

Supplemental Materials

Supplemental Materials for: *Bayesian estimation of geotechnical state variables from penetration and electrical resistivity data: separating density from pore-water salinity*

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This document collects the supplementary analyses cited in the main text: the full per-site field results (Figs. S1-S3); the synthetic method checks—relinearization bias correction, joint localization of a layer boundary, the calibration comparison against sequential inversion and a single ρ -N regression, and the contrast-dependent linearization study (Figs. S4-S7); and the field robustness checks—the soft conductivity prior, lateral fines zonation, the surface-wave (MASW) ablation, the DIPRO comparison, the relative-density consistency check, and the sensitivity of the recovered state to the assumed SPT scatter, to the penetration error model, and to the forward-model coefficients (Figs. S8-S15).

Full Per-Site Field Results

Fig. S1. Full coupled inversion at BH-1 (alluvial): (a) the resistivity section $\rho(x, z)$ implied by the recovered state; (b) the recovered relative-density field $D_r(x, z)$; (c) shear-wave velocity $V_s(x, z)$ reproduced from the raw MASW data; and (d) the posterior blow count at the borehole against the SPT log.

Fig. S2. Full coupled inversion at BH-2 (alluvial); panels as in Fig. S1.

Fig. S3. Full coupled inversion at BH-3 (coastal); panels as in Fig. S1, with the buried conductive (saline) horizon visible in the recovered electrical section.

Synthetic Method Checks

Fig. S4. Successive relinearization on synthetic data: (a) the outer-loop model change decays over iterations (convergence in three to six steps); (b) σ_w recovery—a single linearization leaves a bias in σ_w that the relinearization loop removes; (c) the raw-data electrical misfit.

Fig. S5. Joint localization of a stratigraphic boundary: the joint posterior for the boundary depth Z_b is sharper than the penetration-only or ERT-only posterior—the two data types localize a shared feature better together than either alone.

Fig. S6. Coupled inversion versus sequential inversion versus a single ρ - N regression on held-out synthetic blow count: (a) predicted versus true N ; (b) point accuracy and interval calibration—the coupled estimator attains comparable accuracy but is the only one whose 90% predictive interval retains nominal coverage (97%), against 72% for the overconfident sequential inversion.

Fig. S7. Contrast-dependent DC-forward linearization error on a Pohang-scale survey (21 electrodes): the single-linearization error is small (≈ 0.04) at the alluvial resistivity contrast but large (≈ 0.35 , well above the noise floor) at the coastal contrast; the relinearization loop converges in one to three iterations and removes it. The residual coastal field misfit is therefore a forward-model discrepancy, not a linearization error.

Field Robustness Checks

Fig. S8. Pore-water conductivity $\sigma_w(z)$ under a soft conductivity prior versus the baseline at each site: the buried saline horizon at BH-3 is recovered under both, confirming it is not an artifact of a tight EC prior.

Fig. S9. Lateral fines-zonation test at BH-3: (a) only a large-amplitude lateral fines field improves the electrical fit, and (b) even then it does not reproduce the buried conductive horizon—clay alone cannot account for the conductivity anomaly.

Fig. S10. Surface-wave (MASW) ablation in the field: with MASW on versus off, the σ_w median and the recovered state are essentially unchanged, confirming that MASW enters as a further raw, σ_w -blind density observable.

Fig. S11. Coupled resistivity at each borehole versus a standard DIPRO-inverted section: the coupled estimate and the conventional inversion agree on the resistivity structure.

Fig. S12. Independent check of the recovered relative density (granular layers; clay layers shaded): the coupled D_r posterior agrees with D_r derived independently from SPT N , CPT q_c and V_s single-test correlations at the three boreholes (RMS as annotated).

Fig. S13. Robustness to the assumed SPT scatter (coefficient of variation 0.25–0.60) at the three boreholes: the posterior relative density is stable across the assumed scatter.

Fig. S14. Robustness to the SPT error model: a heavy-tailed Student-t penetration likelihood ($\nu = 4$) leaves (a) the BH-1 relative density and (b) the BH-3 saline horizon unchanged, while (c) modestly improving the coastal SPT predictive coverage (0.64 \rightarrow 0.79).

Fig. S15. Forward-coefficient sensitivity at BH-1: (a) the Archie cementation exponent m and (b) the V_s age factor f_{age} —the recovered state is robust across plausible coefficient ranges.